

VARICOSE VEIN TREATMENT OPTIONS AVAILABLE AT LONG ISLAND SOUTH SHORE

varicose vein treatment near me South Shore has evolved a lot over the years. Until somewhat recently, it involved the use of general anesthesia. Patients would undergo surgery of the groin or thigh area in order to address the problem. This traditional approach, known as stripping, involved pulling diseased or non-functioning vessels from the legs.

To treat this problem, the **vein clinic near me** uses the laser treatment option. Laser lights are heated to 700 degrees Celsius and are used to boil the blood. In response to the damage, scar tissue will form and close off the vein.

The technology employs the use of radio frequencies and catheters to fight this common problem. This [varicose vein treatment South Shore](#) gets to the root of the problem. Patients do not need to be sedated. Instead, a simple local anesthetic is used. They can get back to their normal routine within just a day. Doctors can easily use this approach to address multiple areas in one single visit. Hospitalization is not necessary for this outpatient procedure. Furthermore, patients don't need to worry about recovery time or scarring.

This radio frequency-based procedure is minimally invasive and does not involve surgery of any kind. Instead, a small incision is made in the lower leg area. Into this small opening, a catheter is inserted which allows **vein doctor long island** to access the affected areas.

The doctor uses the catheter and radiofrequency energy to heat up the wall of each vein. This rise in temperature causes collagen in the wall to shrink, which prompts the vein to close.

After it is completely closed off, blood will naturally redirect itself to other healthy, active routes.

Varicose veins are a common issue

Vessel damage is a very common issue in both men and women. It is the result of blood valves not working as they should in specific areas. When this happens, blood collects in those areas and pressure builds up. These affected veins become weaker and larger. They may twist or stick out from the skin on the legs and ankles and are often most noticeable when a person stands. They may have a spider-like appearance or be very dark-colored.

This condition often runs in families, though age and several other factors increase the likelihood of having them. The most significant factors include being pregnant and standing for very long periods of time on a regular basis, such as for work. Though the condition is not completely preventable, [vein treatment South Shore](#) are some things people can do to prevent their likelihood of having this problem, at least at a younger age. Preventative measures include exercising regularly, not standing or sitting for prolonged periods of time without movement, avoiding high heels when possible, and elevating the legs sometimes. As is wise with most medical conditions, people who are predisposed to this problem should maintain a healthy weight and stay active.

There are different types of blood vessels that can be affected by this condition, and anyone considering **vein treatment near me South Shore** should make sure the option they pick can effectively treat their specific condition.